

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842

ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

Vol. IV Issue IV, April 2024

Monthly Issue

International Circulation

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269

DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433

TIN 293-150-678/ Business Permit No. 8183

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WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue IV (April 2024) / International Circulation

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678 / Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

FACTORS AFFECTING JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL SCIENCE PERFORMANCE: BASIS FOR INTERVENTION PROGRAM

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Abstract

The study aimed to determine the factors affecting junior high school performance in Science. Both teachers and struggling students were identified as participants in the study. The results showed that for teachers, the students' performance in science was affected by their poor reading comprehension, lack of mastery of the subject matter, negative attitude, and poor study habits. On the other hand, students indicated that their lack of prior knowledge and teacher incompetence affected their performance in science. Meanwhile, both teachers and students revealed that the use of varied teaching strategies and constant monitoring by parents helped improve students' performance in science. The researcher concluded that despite efforts to reach the ideals of the K-12 curriculum, some learners fail to acquire scientific competence because they have poor skills and attitudes towards science. The researcher recommended that intensive learning interventions be done in order to address the prevailing problems.

Keywords: Junior High School Performance, Science Intervention Program

1. Introduction

The study aims to determine the factors affecting the performance of junior high school learners specifically in the subject science. Likewise, results of the study serves as basis for crafting an instructional enhancement program for the struggling junior high school learners. Science Education faces various challenges, especially in the context of the K to 12 curriculum and the recent shift to distance learning thus, the transition back to face-to-face classes presents its own set of difficulties for learners. Conducting a phenomenological study to identify factors affecting junior high school learners in Salvacion National High School is a crucial step towards crafting effective learning intervention programs in science classes. This research can greatly benefit the students and contribute to improving science education program.

The significance of the study spans from aiding teachers in pedagogy to informing curriculum makers and DepEd officials. The intervention program to be recommended based on the study's results will likely be tailored to address the identified factors influencing performance in science. Further, the study's significance extends to informing teaching

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strategies, aiding struggling learners, and guiding curriculum development. Recommendations from the study will likely lead to tailored intervention programs to address identified performance factors.

The literature review provides various studies related to factors influencing academic performance, particularly in science education. It underscores the significance of teacher quality, instructional methods, and the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on learning outcomes. Project-based learning and professional development are highlighted as essential for engaging students and improving teaching practices. Additionally, it discusses various factors affecting student performance of adequate resources, teacher preparation, and positive attitudes towards science in enhancing student achievement.

The Theoretical framework draws from Thorndike's Learning Readiness Theory, Bruner's Constructivism, and Bandura's Social Learning Theory. The study aims to understand how these theories intersect to influence factors affecting junior high school performance in science.

The conceptual framework presents an input –process-output scheme, depicted in a schematic diagram. The independent variables include factors affecting the performance of junior high school learners, while the dependent variables represent the outcome of the study. Interviews are conducted to gather data on these variables, which are then analysed using thematic analysis to derive findings. Based on the findings, conclusions and recommendations are formulated, leading to the proposal of a science instructional enhancement program for struggling learners. The output is the proposed intervention program, "FACTORS AFFECTING JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL PERFORMANCE: BASIS FOR INTERVENTION PROGRAM".

Methodology

The study employed a descriptive approach and utilized purposive sampling to select participants. A researcher-made interview schedule was used to collect qualitative data. Further, thematic analysis was employed to analyze the data. Prior to the conduct of the study, ethical considerations were considered as such giving consent form to the participants and seeking permission from concerned institutions and departments. There were twenty- three participants in the study, of which twenty were struggling junior high school learners and three Science teachers of Salvacion National High School for school year 2022-2023.

Furthermore, an interview schedule comprising open- ended questions was developed by the researcher in order to determine the factors affecting learners' performance in Science. Participants were engaged in an in-depth interview allowing to express and explain their answers in an open-ended manners. The interview schedule underwent content and face validation to ensure appropriateness.

Data gathering involved seeking permissions and administering consent forms. Face-to- face interviews were conducted observing health protocols. There were also recordings of learners' responses for transcription. Thematic analysis was employed to identify recurring themes and patterns in the collected data.

This comprehensive methodology allowed an in depth exploration of the research topic, providing valuable insights into the factors influencing the academic performance of struggling junior high school learners in Science.

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Results and Discussion

Based on the interview from the participants, the first question was asked on the factors affecting JHS performance in terms of written exam/work, various themes emerged herein such as poor reading comprehension, unmastered skills and poor vocabulary. For teacher's perspective, it was found out that poor comprehension skills of learners and lack of mastery on the subject matter were the common answers.

In terms of performance tasks, teachers indicated that learners' attitude matter. The students' negative attitude towards the outputs given to them led to their poor performance tasks results. On the other hand, students admitted poor self-confidence affected their ability to do their performance task.

In terms of periodical exams, teachers also indicated that learners got low scores in their periodical exam because they don't review before the exam. This was confirmed by the learners when they admitted that they lack focus since they tend to prioritize other activities besides their periodical exams.

Moreover, teachers basically confirmed that the factors hindering the students to perform better in the subject science include students' negative attitude towards the subject since. They also stressed that this was caused by their inability to master the concepts needed to progress towards a more difficult subject matter. This was further catapulted by the teachers' lack of pedagogical skills to deal with students' incompetence.

According to Mapulanga (2019), there are six categories into which the factors affecting performance in science can be divided: (a) administrative; (b) teacher; (c) learner; (d) time allotted to science teaching and learning; (e) assessment; and (f) curriculum-related factors. More precisely, the study found that learners' low scientific knowledge, teachers' unpreparedness, a lack of laboratory supplies, and students' lack of laboratory equipment all contributed to students' poor performance in science classes. The study also discovered that providing teaching and learning resources, engaging students, and enhancing evaluation all contribute to children performing better in science.

As for students, they reiterated that the factors hindering their performance in science included their incompetence towards the subject science.

Facilitating factors were also revealed such as the use of the varied teaching strategies used in the classroom as well as parental support has boosted the morale of the struggling learners. Likewise, students indicated that they considered contextualization of lessons a very big help in their ability to grasp the lessons as a facilitating factor in the learners' performance. It was also noted that to develop a learning intervention to struggling learners and a proposed Science program for Science teachers.

Conclusion

Knowing the factors that affecting Junior High School Performance in terms of written works, performance task, and periodical test would serve as the basis to craft an intervention program for learners in Science as well as propose a program for Science Teachers. In addition, students should develop effective study habits which are crucial for success in learning. For educators, they can implement strategies such as differentiated instruction, targeted interventions, and scaffolding techniques to support students with varying comprehension levels and learning needs and incorporate ICT in science classes. After all, this program aims to promote mastery, innovation, and academic growth to learners and Science teachers.

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Reference:

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DOI 10.5281/zenodo.11033276

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